

Experimental Study of the Effect of Surface Texture in Sliding Contacts Using Infrared Thermography

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of surface texturing on temperature distribution in lubricated sliding contacts using infrared thermography. The work addresses the broader challenge of understanding thermal effects in conformal hydrodynamic contacts, where localized heating and viscosity variations can significantly affect tribological performance. A pin-on-disc configuration was employed, featuring steel pins with laser-etched micro-dimples sliding against a sapphire disc, which allowed for thermal imaging of the contact zone. A dual-bandpass filter infrared thermography technique was developed and rigorously calibrated to distinguish between the temperatures of the steel surface and the lubricant film. Friction measurements and laser-induced fluorescence were used in parallel to assess contact conditions and lubricant film behavior. The results show that surface textures can alter local frictional heating and contribute to non-uniform temperature distributions, particularly in parallel contact geometries. Lubricant temperature was consistently higher than the surface temperature, highlighting the role of shear heating within the fluid film. However, no distinct evidence of a viscosity wedge effect was observed under the tested conditions. The method provides a novel means of experimentally resolving temperature fields in sliding textured contacts, offering a valuable foundation for validating thermo-hydrodynamic models in lubricated tribological systems.

Keywords: Infrared thermography; Surface texturing; Hydrodynamic lubrication; Viscosity-temperature compensation; Pin-on-disc; Thermal effects

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1. Introduction

Lubricated sliding contacts operating in the hydrodynamic lubrication regime are widely used in various engineering applications, including radial and axial bearings, seals, and thrust washers. A modern approach to improving the performance of such components involves the use of surface texturing. Although surface textures have been shown to improve friction and load-carrying characteristics under certain conditions, as summarized in several review papers [1–8], some of the underlying mechanisms remain incompletely understood.

It has been found that thermal effects may have a surprisingly strong influence on the behaviour of textured contact [9]. One of the mechanisms that can have a positive

effect is a so-called viscosity wedge action that was originally described by Cameron more than 65 years ago [10]. This effect arises from a temperature gradient across the lubricant film, typically with a warmer fluid layer near one surface and a cooler one near the other. In numerical studies, the influence of this gradient has been modeled in surface-textured contacts [11–13]. These simulations suggest that in shallow dimples, frictional heating predominantly occurs near the moving surface, enhancing the temperature gradient and supporting the viscosity wedge mechanism. In deeper dimples, stronger recirculation leads to thermal homogenization, thereby reducing the temperature gradient and diminishing the effect. The study [12] reported that inclusion of the viscosity wedge effect in simulations led to a 28-fold increase in load-carrying capacity compared to models that excluded it and the mechanism has the potential to contribute positively to load support even in untextured parallel contacts [14], highlighting the potential importance of this mechanism.

To date, most available information on temperature distributions in textured hydrodynamic contacts originates from numerical simulations. There is a notable lack of experimental data that could verify, challenge, or extend the results of these models. A promising method for experimentally capturing temperature fields in such systems is infrared (IR) thermography. This non-contact technique measures infrared radiation emitted by surfaces and converts it into temperature maps. This method was first applied for temperature mapping in a ball-on-disc configuration [15]. To distinguish the temperature of the steel ball from that of the lubricant, band-pass filters were later introduced, enabling selective acquisition of radiation from different sources based on their characteristic emission wavelengths [16]. While the lubricating oil emits radiation over a narrow wavelength band, the steel ball behaves as a gray body and emits over a broader spectrum. In subsequent developments, a reflective chrome coating was applied to the underside of the sapphire disc to isolate its contribution during calibration [17,18].

Although these methods were developed primarily for ball-on-disc contacts, further advancement enabled estimation of average and even three-dimensional temperature distributions across the lubricant film [19]. However, IR thermography has been rarely applied to pin-on-disc configurations. In those few studies that did explore such geometries, the focus was typically not on spatially resolved temperature measurements within the contact itself [20–22] or on using an optical fiber pyrometer for single-point measurement only [20]. One of the few works using IR thermography to evaluate temperature distribution in contact is an application on mechanical seals [21]. For textured contacts, relevant work includes IR observation of journal-bearing shells from the side (in the axial direction), which enables global thermal effects to be considered, such as compensation for oil temperature variations [22,23].

In recent years, thermal effects have been shown to exert a more significant influence on sliding contacts than previously assumed [24–26]. Frictional heating increases with both sliding speed and applied load. The resulting temperature rise affects the physical properties of the lubricant, which in turn alters the friction and load-carrying performance of the contact. Textured surfaces are particularly susceptible to such temperature-induced changes due to their complex geometries and the associated fluid flow phenomena. Yet, studies that examine these effects in textured contacts remain predominantly theoretical or simulation-based.

The objective of the present work is to implement an infrared thermography method for non-contact temperature measurement in a conformal pin-on-disc configuration and to assess the presence of thermal effects in textured surfaces under controlled experimental conditions in parallel and near-parallel contact configuration.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental setup

The experiments were conducted on a modified Rtec MFT-5000 tribometer in a pin-on-disc configuration (see Figure 1). The device is equipped with strain-gauge force sensors for measuring friction (F_x) and normal load (F_z), as well as precise positioning in three axes. The tribometer was modified to mount a sapphire disc (acting as the transparent counterface) and to hold a steel test pin with fine tilt adjustment for achieving parallel or near-parallel alignment of the contact surfaces. Lubricating oil is held on the upper side of the disc by a rim.

Figure 1. Scheme of the pin-on-disc tribometer.

Figure 2. A photo of the pin-on-disc tribometer with an optical assembly for (a) IR thermography and (b) fluorescence microscopy.

This pin-on-disc configuration is complemented by optical assemblies for IR thermography (see Figure 2(a)) and fluorescence microscopy (see Figure 2(b)). In both cases, the horizontal optical axis is directed into contact with the underside of the disc using an adjustable prism mirror. Temperature measurements were acquired using a FLIR SC5000

scientific-grade IR camera with a 320×265 pixel InSb detector equipped with two narrow-band-pass filters mounted in a filter wheel. Together with an X3 infrared microscope lens it provides a field of view of 3.2×2.4 mm and a maximum frame rate of 380 Hz.

The fluorescence imaging system consisted of a 415 nm LED light source (Thorlabs M415L4), a fluorescence filter cube (comprising excitation and emission filters with a dichroic mirror), a 2x microscope objective, and a monochrome camera (Tucsen FL-20BW). The camera is equipped with a 5472×3648 pixel cooled CMOS sensor ($2.4 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size), providing a field of view of 6.55×4.4 mm. Excitation light was focused into the contact zone through the objective, and the emitted fluorescence was collected along the same path.

2.2. Materials

The test specimens consisted of cylindrical AISI 52100 steel pins with a flat circular contact surface of 5.2 mm in diameter. Surface texturing was applied using a nanosecond-pulsed fiber laser to generate arrays of circular dimples arranged in a triangular pattern, as shown in Figure 3. This pattern ensures theoretical coverage of 19.6 %, but the actual coverage varied depending on the final number of dimples on the surface of the pin. Six textured pins with the parameters summarized in Table 1 were used. Selected pins combined different dimple sizes and depths to explore the influence of texture geometry on hydrodynamic and thermal behavior. Pin C and D (and E and F) had the same texture but differed in their orientation relative to the direction of disc movement. Due to the limitations of laser texturing, the sides of the textures are not perfectly perpendicular, but have an inclination of approximately 40° . Prior to laser processing, the pin surfaces were polished to a mirror-like finish ($R_a < 50$ nm) to ensure uniformity. A smooth, non-textured pin was used as a reference.

Table 1. Texture parameters on the pin surface.

Pin designation	Diameter (μm)	Depth (μm)	Coverage (%)	Orientation
Non-textured	-	-	-	-
Pin A	100	10	17.3	diagonal
Pin B	400	20	14.2	diagonal
Pin C	800	5	16.6	diagonal
Pin D	800	5	16.6	in-line
Pin E	800	10	16.6	diagonal
Pin F	800	10	16.6	in-line

Figure 3. Texture parameters on the pin surface.

The sapphire disc (synthetic single-crystal Al_2O_3 , diameter 160 mm, thickness 5 mm) was selected for its high infrared transparency in the 3–5 μm band and its high mechanical and thermal stability.

The lubricant used in all tests was FVA4 reference oil, a mineral base oil with a kinematic viscosity of 460 mm^2/s at 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ (ISO VG 460). The oil with such a high viscosity was chosen to facilitate the induction of thermal phenomena. The dynamic viscosity of the lubricant was determined by Vogel's model in the form:

$$\eta = A \cdot e^{\frac{B}{t+C}}, \quad (1)$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity of the oil in $\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, t is oil temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$ and constants A , B and C are $A = 3.72 \times 10^{-5}$, $B = 1.33 \times 10^3$ a $C = 1.03 \times 10^2$. To measure film thickness using fluorescence microscopy, the lubricant was stained with the fluorescent dye Coumarine 6.

2.3. Methods – Infrared Thermography

A key aspect of this study is the implementation of an infrared (IR) thermography method for temperature measurement in the sliding contact. To enable separation of the radiation emitted by the steel pin and the lubricant film, two narrow-band IR filters were used in front of the camera sensor, as illustrated in Figure 4. The first filter (denoted S-filter) had a passband centered at 3.410 μm (bandwidth 290 nm) and allowed the combined infrared emission from the oil and the steel pin to be recorded. The second filter (L-filter), centered at 4.672 μm (bandwidth 140 nm), was chosen such that it predominantly transmitted radiation from the steel pin while largely excluding the oil's emission band (since lubricating oil emits IR strongly in a narrower wavelength range around $\sim 3.4 \mu\text{m}$). By alternating these filters, it was possible to capture two sets of IR images: one showing the pin's surface temperature (L-filter) primarily, and another containing both the pin's and oil's contributions (S-filter). Tests were also performed without any filter in the optical path to record the overall radiation as a baseline. There is also the option of measuring the temperature of the disc using a fully reflective chrome coating [17,18]; however, this approach was not used due to the wear and degradation of the coating under demanding test conditions.

Figure 4. The radiation spectrum of individual components, the emission filters used and a scheme of the radiation filtration of individual sources.

Because the camera measures IR intensity in arbitrary units (digital levels, DL), a thorough calibration procedure was required to convert the recorded signals into actual surface temperatures for both the steel pin and the oil film. The calibration was an extended, multi-step process that built upon a method previously developed for point contact (ball-on-disc) measurements [27]. In adapting it to the present conformal contact,

three main calibration steps were performed to account for the different radiation sources and the presence of a lubricant layer, as shown schematically in Figure 5:

1. **Dry calibration with a pin:** First, the steel pin's surface emission was calibrated in a dry state. A custom-built calibration fixture was used, which allowed the test pin (or alternatively a steel ball) to be heated in a controlled manner and pressed against the sapphire disc. The calibration tool consisted of cartridge heaters and a thermocouple, which were used to precisely regulate the temperature of the steel sample via a PID controller. In the dry calibration, the pin (with no oil) was heated stepwise from room temperature up to about 100 °C, and at each plateau the IR camera recorded images through both the L-filter and S-filter. Since no lubricant was present, the L-filter images captured the pin's thermal radiation directly, and the S-filter images captured the same pin radiation but through the other filter. From each pair of images at a given temperature, a filter transmittance factor $k(t)$ was determined to account for the different spectral responses of the two filters. In practice, the raw digital levels from the camera were first fitted as functions of the known temperature (using a quadratic polynomial fit), and then $k(t)$ was obtained from the ratio DL_S/DL_L at each temperature. This step established the relationship between IR intensity and actual temperature for the steel pin surface, for both filter configurations.
2. **Oil calibration with a pin:** The second step introduced a thin layer of oil between the pin and the sapphire disc to calibrate the measurement of lubricant film temperature. Thin metal shims of known thickness (10 μm and 20 μm) were placed under the pin in the calibration fixture to create a controlled oil-filled gap. At each temperature plateau, IR images were recorded with the L-filter and S-filter. Due to the different reflectivity of the surfaces, L and S-filter data were evaluated on both the smooth surface and at the bottom of the dimple. From the L-filter data, digital level values were obtained for the pin surface (smooth area) and the pin dimple. The S-filter data for the smooth surface area provides the combined signal of steel and oil. Using the previously determined $k(t)$ to account for filter differences, the oil film's contribution at each temperature could be isolated by subtracting the appropriately scaled steel signal from the S-filter measurement. This yielded a calibration curve of IR intensity vs. temperature for the lubricant oil film in a thin layer.
3. **Oil calibration with a ball:** The third calibration step was designed to account for the effect of oil film thickness on the measured IR intensity. A steel ball and the sapphire disc were used to create a continuously varying gap. By pressing a steel ball against the sapphire disc with a layer of oil and heating it to a known elevated temperature, a single camera image can capture regions of different film thickness (from the center of contact outwards). The geometry of the ball-on-disc contact was determined using Hertzian contact theory calibrated by an interferometric method [28], so that at each pixel in the IR image the local oil film thickness was known. Based on a relation between the oil's IR signal (DL_{oil}) and the film thickness h , a thickness compensation factor $h(t)$ was introduced. The calibration confirmed that beyond a certain thickness ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ for the FVA4 oil), the recorded IR intensity from the oil stops increasing (the oil layer becomes optically thick, contributing its full black-body emission). So, for oil layers thicker than about 10 μm , $h(t) = 1$ (no correction needed), while for thinner films $h(t) < 1$, proportionally reducing the inferred temperature to account for the reduced emission.

Figure 4. Scheme of the calibration procedure for the IR thermography.

2.4. Methods – Fluorescence microscopy

Lubricant film thickness was evaluated using fluorescence microscopy, a technique that correlates optical intensity with local film thickness. To ensure reliable thickness evaluation, a multi-step calibration procedure was carried out prior to testing (see Figure 5) [29]. The first step involved flat-field correction to eliminate non-uniformities in the illumination field and sensor response. This was performed using a calibration fixture holding a smooth glass pad and 10 μ m-thick spacer shims to create a uniform oil layer of known thickness. Flat-field correction was applied directly in the acquisition software.

To assign absolute film thickness values to fluorescence intensities, a secondary calibration was performed using spacers (10 to 50 μ m thick shims) partially inserted into the contact zone between the pin and the disc. Cross-sectional profiles of the fluorescence image were extracted across this interface. Linear fits to the shim region and the adjacent pin surface were used to calculate the optical gap.

Lubricant film thickness evaluation was performed in three independent profiles, which were evaluated and averaged. The film thickness distribution is evaluated by comparison with the calibration curve. By fitting the film thickness in a smooth area (outside the pits), the actual inclination of the pin is further determined. This allows precise alignment and determination of the instantaneous inclination during the test.

Figure 5. Scheme of the calibration and evaluation procedure for the fluorescence microscopy.

2.5. Experimental procedure and parameters

The aim of this study was to investigate thermal effects, so the test procedure and conditions were chosen to achieve a significant increase in temperature. To generate a Stribeck curve (a plot of the coefficient of friction vs. a viscosity-speed-load parameter), the rotating speed was increased in steps for each load. The rotational speed ranged from 50 rpm to 1400 rpm, corresponding to circumferential sliding speeds from 0.3 m/s to 8.1 m/s. At each speed setpoint, the disc ran for a short duration (4 s) under steady conditions while data were recorded, and then the rotation was stopped for a cooling period of 10–40 s before the next speed step. This start-stop cyclic approach (illustrated schematically in Figure 6) ensured that a temperature rise in the contact was mostly due to the immediate frictional heating at that speed, rather than cumulative bulk heating from the previous steps. The pause allowed the contact to return closer to ambient temperature before each new speed, improving the repeatability of measurements and preventing excessive thermal drift. Four normal loads were used: 5 N, 10 N, 20 N, and 50 N, corresponding to nominal contact pressures (assuming the flat-on-flat apparent contact area of the pin) of approximately 0.2, 0.5, 0.9, and 2.4 MPa, respectively.

The tests were conducted in two pin inclinations: 0.05 degrees representing the wedge gap and 0 degrees representing the parallel surfaces.

Figure 6. Evolution of the IR camera digital level (DL) in the Stribeck curve measurement cycle for one load, including 4s rotation periods and cooling periods.

- Each test sequence (covering all speeds for a given load) was conducted four times: 266
- IR optical setup with L-filter; 267
 - IR optical setup with S-filter; 268
 - IR optical setup with no filter; 269
 - Fluorescence optical setup for lubricant film thickness measurement. 270

Before each measurement, a reference image of the static contact was taken to be subtracted as a “background” for temperature evaluation, and a flat-field correction was made for fluorescence imaging. This procedure was time-consuming and required strict adherence to test conditions, but it enabled the application of a robust temperature distribution evaluation. 271–275

Using the established calibration curves, the relative increase in temperature of the oil and the pin surface was obtained for each step. The maximum temperature in the contact typically occurred at the end of the 4 s running period, and this was taken as the representative contact temperature for that speed and load. Because of a limited field-of-view of IR optical system, the view is directed toward the center of the pin. In addition to the temperature obtained by filtering individual radiation sources, an “average temperature” is also evaluated, which is determined based on measurements and calibrations without the filters. The experimental data were then used to construct Stribeck curves (COF vs. a velocity or viscosity-speed parameter) for each tested pin and condition. 276–284

3. Results 285

3.1. Temperature measurement 286

Typical examples of the temperature field obtained from the infrared thermography setup are shown in Figure 7. The left image represents the surface temperature of the pin, while the right image shows the temperature of the lubricant film. It should be noted that the pin temperature map is composed of two separately calibrated regions: the flat surface outside the dimples (“Pin – flat”) and the dimple interiors (“Pin – dimple”). For further analysis, the temperature values are evaluated over two regions of interest: (i) an area corresponding to a single dimple and (ii) an annular region surrounding the dimple in the central part of the pin. The temperature differences between the dimple and flat regions are apparent, especially for the pin temperature. The oil temperature exhibits much higher noise, which is a consequence of the calibration procedure: after subtracting the L-filter signal, the remaining oil contribution corresponds to only a small range of digital levels. 287–297

Figure 7. Typical temperature fields of the pin surface and lubricant film obtained by infrared thermography for Pin E ($800 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ dimples in a diagonal arrangement) at 50 N and 8.1 m/s. 298–300

Figure 8 summarizes the relative temperature rise as a function of sliding speed for the large-dimple pin E ($800 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ dimples) at the highest load of 50 N, for both parallel and inclined (0.05°) contacts. Relative temperature is defined as the increase in temperature with respect to the initial reference temperature of the oil in a bath. In both contact 301–304

geometries, the temperature of the lubricant and of the pin increases almost linearly with sliding speed, which is well captured by a second-order polynomial fit. The lubricant temperature is systematically higher than the temperature of the pin surface, confirming that shear heating in the oil film is the dominant source of heat generation. Within the pin, the temperature in the dimple region is slightly higher than on the surrounding flat area, indicating a modest local intensification of shear and/or reduced heat dissipation inside the texture. For the oil, the difference between the dimple and flat regions is present but less pronounced. The “average” temperature measured without spectral filtering is significantly lower than both the oil and pin temperatures; this confirms that unfiltered thermography underestimates the actual fluid and surface temperatures in the contact zone. Parallel contacts exhibit higher overall temperatures than inclined contacts, which is consistent with the higher coefficients of friction observed in the parallel configuration.

Figure 8. Relative pin and oil temperatures in the dimple and flat regions as a function of sliding speed for pin E at 50 N in parallel and inclined (0.05°) contacts.

3.2. Friction measurement

The coefficient of friction (COF) was analyzed as a function of the combined parameter including sliding speed u (m/s), lubricant viscosity η (Pa·s), and applied normal force F (N). Figure 9 illustrates the influence of different viscosity-correction approaches on the Stribeck curve for a parallel contact with pin C ($800 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$). When viscosity is calculated at a fixed reference temperature (thermocouple in the oil bath, approximately room temperature), the COF data deviate markedly from the expected power-law trend, especially at higher loads and speeds. Using the “average” temperature from unfiltered IR measurements partially reduces this deviation, but significant scatter remains, and the points still deviate from a single master curve as the temperature increases.

Figure 9. Effect of different viscosity corrections on the Stribeck behaviour for the parallel configuration with pin C ($800 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$), showing that only the correction based on instantaneous oil temperature collapses the data onto a single trend.

The most consistent behaviour is obtained when viscosity is corrected using the instantaneous oil temperature measured in the flat region outside the dimples (“Oil – flat”). In this case, the data collapse onto a nearly single power-law trend over the whole range of loads and speeds, independent of the local operating temperature. This confirms that the apparent non-linearity in the uncorrected Stribeck curves is largely a consequence of temperature-induced viscosity variations rather than changes in the lubrication regime.

When this final correction is applied, data for all pins and both contact geometries can be plotted together, as shown in Figure 10. In the parallel configuration, all textured pins and the smooth reference pin fall within a relatively narrow band, with only modest differences between texture designs. The inclined configuration (0.05°) yields generally lower COF values and a tighter alignment of points along the power-law trend, indicating more stable hydrodynamic lubrication due to the controlled wedge.

Figure 10. Stribeck curves corrected using in-contact oil temperature for all texture patterns in parallel and inclined (0.05°) contacts.

Figure 11 shows the same corrected friction data, colored by the oil temperature. This representation highlights that a wide range of contact temperatures (from ~23 °C to over 60–70 °C) leads to very similar COF when viscosity is properly corrected, further underlining the importance and effectiveness of the temperature-based correction.

Figure 11. Stribeck curves corrected using in-contact oil temperature for all texture patterns in parallel and inclined (0.05°) contacts (same as in Figure 10), with data points colored by oil temperature in the contact.

If we look at the effect of texture on friction, then for parallel contacts, the best results are provided by large dimples with in-line orientation (Pin F and Pin D), where COF is, on average 25% lower than with smooth pin. The only pin that provides higher friction

than the non-textured pin is pin A, which has the smallest dimple diameter. For parallel surfaces, the effect of individual texture patterns is different. The highest friction has non-textured pin and pin A, on the other hand, comes out best. Pin F with large dimples performs the worst. Overall, texturing provides a small but systematic reduction in friction relative to the smooth pin; however, once viscosity is corrected using the local oil temperature, these differences are of the order of 10–15% and do not indicate a dramatic enhancement of hydrodynamic performance under the tested conditions.

3.3. Lubricant Film Thickness Measurement

The lubricant film thickness was measured by fluorescence microscopy and evaluated as a function of the same combined parameter on y axis. Figure 12 show results for pin C ($800 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$) for both parallel and inclined contacts, with points colored by oil temperature.

Figure 12. Lubricant film thickness as a function of the combined parameter for pin C ($800 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$) in parallel and inclined (0.05°) contacts, together with typical intensity maps from fluorescence imaging showing cavitation in parallel contacts (the arrows indicate lubricant flow).

In the parallel configuration, the film thickness exhibits a large scatter and frequently falls below $10 \mu\text{m}$. This regime is particularly sensitive to small variations in alignment and to dynamic effects, such as disc run-out, which can lead to intermittent thinning and local rupture of the film. The scatter is further enhanced by cavitation between individual dimples, resulting in rapid changes in oil film thickness, as illustrated by the intensity maps from fluorescence imaging in Figure 12. Therefore, there is no clear correlation between film thickness and the combined parameter, and the data does not fit a clear trend in the same way as the friction data after viscosity correction.

In the inclined configuration, the lubricant film thickness remains consistently above $10 \mu\text{m}$ over most of the measured range and increases moderately with the increasing characteristic number. This indicates robust full-film hydrodynamic lubrication in the wedge contact.

3.4. Local effects

One of the study's aims was to investigate the local thermal effects occurring in dimples. It was found that some "local effects" can be observed in dimples using IR

thermography; however, these are more likely to be the result of local changes in film thickness rather than local changes in temperature. Some examples are shown in Figure 13, highlighting the complexity of the problem. The following interpretation is based on high-speed IR observation of the contact, which enabled the estimation of lubricant flow in the dimples.

Figure 13. IR images showing local phenomena connected with a cavitation in dimples for different pins and contact configurations; the arrows show lubricant flow direction.

In the parallel configuration, cavitation occurred frequently. Panel (a) shows cavitation in and behind the dimple, while a part of the dimple is filled with lubricant. The inclined oil layer creates interference fringes even in the case of an IR optical system. In case (b), cavitation occurs in the same way, but there is no longer any lubricant in the cavity. For the smaller dimples in panel (c), partial cavitation occurs in some lines of dimples. For the wedge-gaped contacts, cavitation usually occurs only in the dimples. In case (d), interference fringes are visible within the cavitated region, indicating a thin residual film of lubricant trapped at the dimple bottom and a locally varying film thickness. Panels (e) and (f) depict contacts without cavitation in the dimples, corresponding to conditions with more stable lubrication. It should be noted that the annular elements in the dents in image (f) correspond to the actual shape of the pit bottom, which is not completely smooth.

4. Discussion

4.1. Temperature distribution in textured contacts

The infrared measurements revealed that the lubricant and solid pin temperatures were locally higher inside the micro-dimple pockets. This qualitatively agrees with the idea that surface texture creates non-uniform flow and heat fields. For example, thermo-hydrodynamic simulations of textured contacts predict significant local temperature variations in and around pockets [12]. Experimental studies in analogous textured lubrication systems likewise find that the shape and arrangement of texture patterns strongly influence thermal fields [21].

The higher surface temperature measured above the dimples, despite the locally increased film thickness, can be explained by the altered hydrodynamic conditions generated by micro-texturing [12]. Dimple introduces a characteristic pressure redistribution, featuring a pressure drop at its inlet and a rapid pressure recovery at the outlet, which forms a converging wedge that promotes locally intensified shear and viscous dissipation. Theoretical recirculation zones and cavitation inside the dimple modify the local flow field in a way that increases energy losses relative to a smooth surface, even when the global lubrication regime remains hydrodynamic. According to the simulations, the temperature maximum does not occur at the centre of the dimple but near its trailing edge, where reconstruction of the pressure field and film geometry is most pronounced. However, this has not been confirmed in our case.

4.2. Temperature-based viscosity correction

To account for thermal effects on viscosity, the instantaneous oil-film temperature in each test point was used. This differs from some prior approaches that relied on indirect measurements, e.g., [23] monitored journal bearing temperature with an embedded thermocouple in the housing and assumed it represented the film temperature. By contrast, our infrared method measures the local lubricant temperature in situ, capturing transient and spatial variations. In practice, using the local oil temperature yields a more direct estimate of the film's viscosity than a "side" or housing measurement. However, the IR technique requires careful calibration and access through an optical window, whereas a thermocouple is simpler and robust.

By comparing the filtration method based on instantaneous lubricant temperature and the "average IR" temperature, oil temperature compensation proves to be more accurate, as shown in Figure 9 for parallel contacts. When the contact conditions are less severe in terms of temperature and friction power, compensation using the average instantaneous contact temperature also provides reasonable results, and this measurement method is much simpler than using two narrow-band filters.

4.3. Effect of surface texturing parameters

The primary objective of this study was not to investigate the influence of texture parameters or to find optimal parameters for given operating conditions, but rather to demonstrate the influence of temperature compensation on textures of different sizes. Relatively large textures were chosen primarily to facilitate the observation of local phenomena. However, it was still found that textures mostly have a positive effect on friction. When considering the temperature-viscosity compensation, it is evident that it moves points on the Stribeck curve to the left. When comparing COF with the temperature at which compensation was performed (see Figure 14 for inclined contacts), we observe a correlation indicating that higher temperatures are associated with higher friction, so the temperature is a consequence of higher friction.

Once the viscosity correction based on local oil temperature was applied, friction differences between pins narrowed significantly. Textured surfaces still showed a small but systematic reduction in COF, typically 10–15% lower than the smooth surface. However, this reduction does not reflect a fundamental shift in the lubrication regime; rather, it stems from temperature-induced changes in viscosity that affect each configuration differently. The lowest COF provides Pin E with an in-line dimple configuration, which may be surprising, because diagonal texturing is often preferred in a hydrodynamic regime. This contradiction is probably related to improved lubricant entrainment and flow continuity. Overall, the data suggest that under the tested hydrodynamic conditions, surface texturing can marginally reduce friction; however, its benefit depends strongly on the texture scale, pattern orientation, and local thermal effects.

Figure 14. The relative oil temperature used for temperature-viscosity compensation in Figures 10 and 11 for inclined contacts and the highest load of 50 N.

4.4. Local thermal effects

This work hypothesizes that the thermal effects could be “qualitative,” where the relation between friction and temperature lies simply in a change in viscosity, and “quantitative,” causing other changes in friction, such as variations in lubricant film thickness. Since the Stribeck curves in Figures 10 and 11 follow a power-law trend, it can be assumed that the influence of thermal phenomena is only “qualitative” and that, within the scope of the conditions studied, there are no other thermal phenomena that would cause a change in the trend. The qualitative effects, such as “temperature-viscosity wedge action” should be observable in the local temperature distribution.

Based on numerical studies [11,13,30], it can be assumed that these phenomena are most likely to be observable on parallel surfaces. Although according to some theories, cavitation is a phenomenon enabling the lubrication mechanisms of parallel surfaces [31] it could prevent other supporting phenomena from occurring. Experiments with parallel surfaces are very challenging due to cavitation, which is not steady but changes dynamically with the system's dynamics, especially at very high speeds necessary for observing these phenomena. Therefore, observing the temperature distribution in the dimples, for example, due to lubricant circulation, is difficult and requires further work on the IR method and experimental setup.

The experiments probably did not achieve conditions under which local thermal effects would have developed. Such effects typically require very high pressures or shear to develop. Under our moderate-load and speed, fully flooded test conditions, no clear viscosity wedge behavior was observed. In particular, the measured friction did not deviate from the prediction based on the uniform, corrected-viscosity Stribeck response. In other words, our data show no evidence that a strong thermal wedge formed in the contact. However, it should be emphasized that, unlike non-conformal contacts [32–35], this phenomenon has not been experimentally confirmed in conformist contacts.

4.5. IR thermography strengths and limitations

The infrared thermography technique offers significant advantages for studying lubricated contacts. It is non-contact and spatially resolved, providing full maps of temperature on both the oil film and the surfaces. This in-situ imaging is valuable for validating thermal models. The trade-off is that IR measurements are complex: each test requires careful calibration and a sequence of measurements that cannot be performed consecutively within a single test due to constantly increasing temperatures or the need to replace

the optical system. Compared to established procedures used in point contacts, the examined system is more complex and introduces several challenges. Attention must be given to calibration accuracy, as conformal contacts typically show lower “flash” temperatures. At these lower temperatures, the method faces limitations—especially when optical filters are used—because the signal captured by the camera sensor is weaker, making it difficult to reliably evaluate small temperature changes.

A meaningful simplification may be to evaluate only the “average” temperature, where optical filters are not used, but at the cost of not being able to distinguish between radiation sources. To compensate solely for viscosity based on instantaneous temperature, this approach may be sufficiently representative for lower speeds and loads, as well as inclined surfaces. Another significant complexity is the need to measure the film's thickness to compensate for its influence. IR calibration showed that the thickness-dependent emissivity effects are negligible for films thicker than $\sim 10\ \mu\text{m}$. So, the film-thickness corrections may not be necessary if there is certainty that the film thickness is greater.

The biggest challenge of this approach is measuring in a cavitation region. Our results indicate that cavitation has a strong influence on the apparent IR signal, even when using an L filter, which should exclude the influence of the lubricant. Vapor regions emit and transmit infrared radiation differently from liquid-filled zones, particularly when filters are used to suppress oil emission. As a result, cavitation can mask or distort subtle local temperature variations that might be expected from mechanisms such as viscosity-wedge formation. The combined evidence suggests that, under the present test conditions, cavitation and dynamic film instabilities in nominally parallel contacts dominate the local thermal response, making it difficult to unambiguously detect small-scale thermal effects directly attributable to surface texturing alone. In contrast, the inclined contacts show smoother temperature fields and fewer cavitation-related artefacts, but there the thermal gradients are smaller, again limiting the detectability of a clear viscosity wedge signature. More precise targeting of the method is the subject of further work.

5. Conclusions

A robust experimental method based on infrared thermography was developed to assess temperature distributions in hydrodynamic sliding contacts with textured surfaces. The method enabled independent evaluation of lubricant and surface temperatures in a pin-on-disc configuration and was validated through viscosity correction of friction data.

Key findings include:

- Lubricant temperature consistently exceeded surface temperature, confirming shear heating in the fluid as the dominant source of frictional heat.
- Local thermal variations were observed, with slightly elevated temperatures in dimples, but no experimental evidence of a viscosity-wedge effect under the tested conditions.
- Correcting lubricant viscosity using instantaneous oil temperature improved the alignment of Stribeck curves, highlighting the necessity of accounting for local temperature when evaluating tribological behavior.
- The influence of surface textures on friction was modest; after viscosity correction, differences narrowed to 10–15%, with in-line dimples generally performing best.
- Cavitation and film instability in parallel contacts posed challenges for IR evaluation and likely obscured subtle local thermal effects.

The technique provides a valuable tool for experimental validation of numerical models. Future work will aim to improve resolution in cavitating zones and explore higher-speed or higher-pressure regimes where thermal wedge effects may be more pronounced.

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